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Report on limit of
detection of amplicon-
based and shotgun
metagenomics

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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2

REPORT ON LIMIT OF DETECTION OF AMPLICON-BASED AND SHOTGUN METAGENOMICS

**This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation**

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>)

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Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE–WP2 NGS-based genomics and metagenomics

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Task:

**JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP2-T3 Experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics
for detection of foodborne parasites**

Task leader: Rune C. Stensvold, SSI; Deputy Task Leader: Simone M. Cacciò, ISS

1. Background

The PARADISE project aims to deliver informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for the food-borne parasites *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using genomics and metagenomics, the project is generating much needed data to enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis for development and testing of improved strain-typing schemes. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices are under development and validation. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches to control *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in the European food chain. Within WP2, the main objectives were: 1) to generate novel genome data from selected isolates of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* in WP2-T1; 2) to use in silico approaches and a referenced database to interrogate available metagenomes to detect foodborne parasites in WP2-T2; and 3) to use amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics approaches to detect target parasites using spiked food matrices in WP2-T3.

This report deals with the WP2-Task3 “Experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics for detection of foodborne parasites”, and specifically with the efforts to determine the limit of detection of amplicon-based and shotgun-based metagenomics approaches.

2. Introduction

Amplicon-based and shotgun-based metagenomics approaches have been used for taxonomic profiling of bacterial and viral communities present in different matrices (faeces, other biological samples, environmental and food samples). Their application to parasitic pathogens is more limited, and less is known on the relative performance of these methodologies. Accordingly, the main objective of the experiments described here was to compare the limit of detection of the two metagenomics approaches using a panel of samples (plant matrix) spiked with known amounts of parasitic targets.

3. Spiking experiments

To mimic natural contamination of a vegetable matrix, we spiked DNA extracted from a ready-to-eat salad with DNA from three parasites (*Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Giardia duodenalis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*). The amount of plant DNA (3 µg) corresponded to the average amount obtained after the elution procedure routinely used when processing a plant matrix for the detection of parasites. The amount of parasite DNA was calculated taken into account the genome size and the number of nuclei present in a single (oo)cyst, and three spike levels were prepared to mimic the presence of 10, 50 and 100 (oo)cysts. A negative control completed the sample panel (Table 1). The panel was prepared by P-8 (VRI) and sent with bind codes to P-13 (SSI) and P-27 (ISS). Partner P-30 (RIVM) was involved in the analyses of the shotgun data generated by P-27.

Table 1. Composition of the sample panel.

Code	Plant DNA	<i>C. parvum</i> oocysts (DNA equivalent)	<i>G. duodenalis</i> cysts (DNA equivalent)	<i>T. gondii</i> oocysts (DNA equivalent)
VRI-1	3 µg	//	50 (15 pg)	//
VRI-2	3 µg	100 (4 pg)	//	//
VRI-3	3 µg	//	//	100 (56 pg)
VRI-4	3 µg	//	100 (30 pg)	//
VRI-5	3 µg	10 (0.4 pg)	//	//
VRI-6	3 µg	//	//	10 (5,6 pg)
VRI-7	3 µg	//	10 (3 pg)	//
VRI-8	3 µg	//	//	50 (28 pg)
VRI-9	3 µg	50 (2 pg)	//	//
VRI-10	3 µg	//	//	//

3. Metabarcoding assay

The metabarcoding assay was applied to the panel of spiked samples at P-13 (SSI). The samples were tested in parallel by in-house qPCR protocols targeting each parasite. As shown in Table 2, the qPCR detected the three parasites at the three spike levels, although the Ct values were not always proportional to the amount of DNA used for the spikes. On the other hand, the metabarcoding assay only detected *Toxoplasma gondii*, and only at the two highest spiking levels (Table 2).

This suggests that the limit of detection of the metabarcoding assay is >100 *C. parvum* oocysts and >100 *G. duodenalis* cysts, while it is between 50 and 100 oocysts for *T. gondii*.

Table 2. Results of qPCR and metabarcoding assays on the panel of spikes.

Sample	<i>Cryptosporidium</i>		<i>Giardia</i>		<i>Toxoplasma</i>	
	qPCR result (Ct value)	Metabarcoding result	qPCR result (Ct value)	Metabarcoding result	qPCR result (Ct value)	Metabarcoding result
VRI-1	negative	negative	Positive (25.6)	Negative	negative	negative
VRI-2	Positive (31.5)	Negative	negative	negative	negative	negative
VRI-3	negative	negative	negative	negative	Positive (28.8)	Positive
VRI-4	negative	negative	Positive (24.8)	Negative	negative	negative
VRI-5	Positive (33.3)	Negative	negative	negative	negative	negative
VRI-6	negative	negative	negative	negative	Positive (32.0)	Negative
VRI-7	negative	negative	Positive (30.7)	Negative	negative	negative
VRI-8	negative	negative	negative	negative	Positive (30.4)	Positive
VRI-9	Positive (28.3)	Negative	negative	negative	negative	negative
VRI-10	negative	negative	negative	negative	negative	negative

4. Shotgun metagenomics

The same panel in Table 1 was used for shotgun experiments. Library preparation and Illumina sequencing (2x150 b paired ends) were outsourced to a commercial service. Data analyses were undertaken at P-27 and P-30, based on BWA or Kraken followed by BLAST searches of the reads putatively assigned to each target parasite. The results did not confirm the presence of the parasite in

the expected samples, and were difficult to explain. As shown in Table 3, there was no correspondence between the panel composition and the reads assigned to each parasite species.

Table 3. Number of parasite reads detected by Kraken2 and confirmed by BLAST in plant DNA samples spiked with different amounts of *C. parvum*, *G. duodenalis* or *T. gondii* DNA.

Sample	<i>C. parvum</i>	<i>G. duodenalis</i>	<i>T. gondii</i>	Spiked with
VRI1	0	0	0	<i>G. duodenalis</i> 50 cysts
VRI2	0	0	0	<i>C. parvum</i> 100 oocysts
VRI3	0	40	8	<i>T. gondii</i> 100 oocysts
VRI4	0	0	0	<i>G. duodenalis</i> 100 cysts
VRI5	0	0	0	<i>C. parvum</i> 10 oocysts
VRI6	501	0	0	<i>T. gondii</i> 10 oocysts
VRI7	542	0	0	<i>G. duodenalis</i> 10 cysts
VRI8	466	0	0	<i>T. gondii</i> 50 oocysts
VRI9	695	8	0	<i>C. parvum</i> 50 oocysts
VRI10	593	12	0	no spike

In view of the inconsistent results, a second set of spikes was prepared at ISS, and a decision was taken to explore a wider range of spikes and to focus on *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*. In this experiment, genomic DNA from a different plant matrix (baby spinach) was used. The plant DNA (1 µg) was spiked with serial dilutions of parasite DNA, from 10 nanograms to 1 picogram. A negative control (plant DNA only) was included in the panel (Tables 4 and 5). The samples were sequenced using Illumina (2x150 bp, paired ends), with production of an average number of 13589016 reads for *C. parvum* and of 65936647 for *G. duodenalis*.

The analyses were based on Kraken2/Braken and the reads assigned to *C. parvum* or to *G. duodenalis* were systematically screened by BLAST against the non-redundant NCBI database. As shown in Table 4, a significant number of reads, confirmed as *C. parvum* by BLAST, was detected in the first three spikes. This suggests that the limit of detection is close to 100 picograms, or about 2500 oocysts.

Table 4. Number of reads detected by Kraken as *C. parvum* and number of reads confirmed by BLAST in plant DNA samples spiked with different amounts of *C. parvum* DNA.

Sample	Plant DNA	<i>C. parvum</i> DNA	N of reads	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>C. parvum</i> (relative abundance)	N of reads confirmed by BLAST
CrMET1	1 µg	10 nanograms	13122427	24928 (1.9×10^{-3})	5374
CrMET2	1 µg	1 nanogram	15080218	3453 (2.3×10^{-4})	634
CrMET3	1 µg	100 picograms	14589873	147 (1×10^{-5})	35
CrMET4	1 µg	10 picograms	12340667	38 (3×10^{-6})	1
CrMET5	1 µg	1 picogram	14314820	37 (2.5×10^{-6})	0
CrMET6	1 µg	No DNA	12086094	35 (2.8×10^{-6})	3

For *G. duodenalis* (Table 5), a significant number of reads, confirmed as *G. duodenalis* by BLAST, was detected in the first four/five spikes. This suggests that the limit of detection is between 1 and 10 picograms, or about 3 to 30 cysts.

Table 5. Number of reads detected by Kraken as *G. duodenalis* and number of reads confirmed by BLAST in plant DNA samples spiked with different amounts of *G. duodenalis* DNA.

Sample	Plant DNA	<i>G. duodenalis</i> DNA	N of reads	N of reads assigned by Kraken to <i>G. duodenalis</i> (relative abundance)	N of reads confirmed by BLAST
GMET1	1 µg	10 nanograms	52965068	134267 (2.5×10^{-3})	75051
GMET2	1 µg	1 nanogram	57683432	13547 (2.3×10^{-4})	8758
GMET3	1 µg	100 picograms	69434672	1702 (2.4×10^{-5})	810
GMET4	1 µg	10 picograms	70465268	311 (4.4×10^{-6})	70
GMET5	1 µg	1 picogram	97788126	262 (2.7×10^{-6})	5
GMET6	1 µg	No DNA	47283320	106 (2.2×10^{-6})	1

5. Conclusions

The application of the metabarcoding assay to a panel of nine spiked samples suggested a relatively low limit of detection for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*, i.e., greater than 100 (oo)cysts, while for *T. gondii* the limit was found to be between 50 and 100 oocysts. The low sensitivity of the metabarcoding assay in the detection of flagellates (including *Giardia*) was expected. When shotgun sequencing was applied to the same panel, inconsistent results were obtained, possibly pointing to technical errors in either the library preparation or during shotgun sequencing. Indeed, when a second set of spikes was prepared and sequenced, results were in line with the expectations, and data analyses suggested a limit of detection close to 3-30 cysts for *G. duodenalis* and close to 2500 oocysts for *C. parvum*, at the applied sequencing depths. As these results are based on a single series of spikes, no firm conclusions can be drawn. However, the experience learned clearly indicated that the signal originating from the eukaryotic background material (i.e., from the plant matrix) can be misinterpreted as originating from the parasite(s), and this calls for a systematic screening of the reads by BLAST against the non-redundant

NCBI database. In addition, the sequencing depth applied for the second *G. duodenalis* experiment was higher compared to that of the second *C. parvum* experiment, and more reads were assigned to *Giardia* than to *Cryptosporidium*, indicating that with higher sequencing depths it is possible to reach a higher sensitivity of detection.